

D2.2

Final report on framework on guidance protocols

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Abstract

The MYRIAD-EU project responds to the growing need for comprehensive frameworks to assess and manage risks arising from multi-hazard and multi-sectoral interactions. While multi-hazard events account for a minority of disaster records, they are responsible for a disproportionate share of global economic losses, highlighting the limitations of traditional single-hazard approaches. To address this, MYRIAD-EU developed and tested a flexible, integrative framework for multi-hazard, multi-risk, and systemic risk management across five diverse European pilot regions. This report presents the final version of the MYRIAD-EU framework and accompanying guidance protocols, refined through four years of implementation and iterative feedback. Drawing on document reviews, survey responses, and focus group discussions with pilots, the report synthesizes key lessons from operationalizing the framework and outlines updates that enhance its usability and applicability. The deliverable serves as a practical resource for stakeholders seeking to integrate multi-hazard risk considerations into disaster risk reduction planning and decision-making.

Dissemination level of the document

Public

Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

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1. Introduction

Multi-hazards and their impacts are increasingly seen as a priority for the science, policy and practice of disaster risk reduction. There is emerging evidence on the urgency for moving from single-hazards and single-sector based approaches to risk assessment and management to multi-hazard and multi-sectoral approaches. MYRIAD-EU has set out to fill this gap and develop and test a first harmonized multi-hazard and multi-risk assessment and management framework. The initial framework was first presented in Deliverable 2.1 (Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2022), submitted in M12, and included the foundations for individual, multi-, and systemic risk analysis and management with potential applications to a range of natural hazards, their interactions, and a variety of sectors. D2.1 also introduced an initial version of the guidance protocols, developed to support the implementation of the framework in five pilot regions of MYRIAD-EU (i.e., Canary Islands, Veneto Region, Danube Region, Scandinavia, and North Sea). As described in D2.1., the framework was defined as a frame one (stakeholders, policy makers, politicians, etc.) can work with, and it does not prescribe specific tools, methods, and approaches for understanding risk assessment, but it rather provides a broad framing that is capable of incorporating a variety of tools, methods and approaches developed within MYRIAD-EU and beyond.

Over the last four years, MYRIAD-EU pilot regions have been implementing the framework with the final aim of developing a rich understanding of multi-(hazard) risk in their areas and choosing risk management options that will directly feed into their forward looking disaster risk management pathways for various sectors of interest. To do so, the five MYRIAD-EU Pilots (North Sea, Canary Islands, Scandinavia, Danube, and Veneto) work closely together with regional authorities, sectoral representatives, and risk managers to address local sustainability challenges. Pilots' experiences with the implementation present a unique opportunity to take stock of learnings of implementation and feed those learnings into the final version of the framework and associated guidance protocols. In this deliverable, Work package 2 (WP2) presents the final version of the framework and guidance protocols. This deliverable is based on the learnings from the past four years, captured in this deliverable through three main data sources: 1) review of deliverables and milestones coming from the WP2 and WP3, 2) an online survey with pilot leads, and 3) a focus group discussion with pilot leads.

This deliverable is organised as follows. **Section 2** gives a short recap of the MYRIAD-EU framework and the logic underlying the guidance protocols. In **Section 3**, we detail the process of framework and guidance protocols updates throughout the lifecycle of MYRIAD-EU. **Section 4** provides a detailed analysis of three streams of feedback (i.e., document review, survey, and a focus group), while **Section 5** outlines the approach for addressing the feedback received. **Section 6** then provides some final reflections on the framework and process of updating. In the **Appendix**, we present a final version of the guidance protocols, where the majority of feedback has been integrated.

2. A short recap of the framework and guidance protocols

2.1. Framework

The MYRIAD-EU framework is presented in Figure 1, with a short description of the framework steps provided below. A comprehensive framework description is available in Deliverable 2.1 (Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2022) and the accompanying academic article (Hochrainer-Stigler et al. 2023).

Figure 1 MYRIAD-EU framework for individual, multi- and systemic risk analysis, and management

General logic of the framework

The framework was developed based on key insights from systemic risk research merged with research on multi-hazards and multi-risk. It is based on two fundamental ideas from systemic risk: (1) system definition (i.e., establishment of clear system boundaries and system elements), and (2) the dependencies between system elements. The framework adopts a “system-of-systems” approach, which allows the necessary level of complexity with an explicit focus on dependencies. These dependencies can be hazard or risk-related. Dependencies allow for the integration of single, multiple, and systemic risks within one coherent framework. Indeed, if no dependencies exist, multiple hazards or risks can be treated as single risks. Conversely, single and systemic risks sit at opposite ends of a continuum, with increasing interdependence marking the transition to multi-risk. Building on these insights, the framework presents a six-step process for analyzing and managing risks across that spectrum, from single to multi- and systemic risk. The framework is further building on the existing multi-hazard and disaster risk management framework and follows the well-established procedures of the risk assessment process according to ISO31010 norms, as explained in detail by Hochrainer-Stigler et al. (2023).

step 1: Finding a system definition

This step starts with a thorough system definition that establishes clear system boundaries and identifies the system's constituent elements. Establishing system boundaries (e.g., geographic, administrative, policy-based, sectoral, or hazard-specific) reduces complexity and distinguishes what lies inside the system from what remains outside.

A clear system understanding then turns to the identification of the sustainability challenge that motivates the analysis (e.g., spill-over effects in the Danube Region or resilience to multi-hazards of island regions dependent on tourism in the Canary Islands). Framing the exercise around a concrete challenge can make natural-hazard research more directly useful for the overall development of the region and directly supports a solution-oriented approach in which possible risk management options and broader solutions are identified early.

An important aspect of system definition is mapping the governance landscape: key policies, institutions, and actors, plus the gaps that currently hinder the system's desired trajectory to reach a sustainability challenge. This can clarify policy targets, reveal the complexity of decision-making (Scolobig et al., 2017), and highlight any existing risk management measures alongside their shortcomings.

Because the framework centres on natural-hazard-related risk, the system definition also needs to identify relevant hazards and possible multi-hazard combinations of interest (i.e., single hazards as well as hazard interrelationships such as cascading or compound hazards). Finally, the system definitions also identify the exposure and vulnerability: the assets and populations situated in hazard-prone areas and the economic, social, institutional, and physical dimensions that shape their susceptibility.

step 2: Characterisation of direct risk

Here, the framework focuses explicitly on direct risk; in other words, risk arising from direct contact between exposed, vulnerable elements and a hazard (e.g., earthquake) or a multi-hazard event (e.g., consecutive floods and droughts). Both exposure and vulnerability are dynamic in a multi-hazard scenario (e.g., buildings destabilized by an earthquake then struck by volcanic ash; households impoverished by hazard A before facing hazard B; displaced populations from hazard A moving to an area exposed to hazard B), and the framework envisions this to be captured in this step.

Determining direct risk further entails selecting risk metrics. This should be done through a stakeholder dialogue to reflect the priorities of decision makers and other relevant stakeholders. Direct risk metrics may include, for instance, physical asset losses, casualties, or the proportion of the population incurring financial setbacks.

step 3: Characterisation of indirect risk

Indirect risk refers to risks and losses that unfold through system interdependencies once direct risk has materialised. For example, agricultural revenue declines following transport-network damage and ripples through supply chains. These indirect impacts can be tangible (e.g., industrial production shortfalls, business-interruption costs) or intangible (e.g., deteriorating mental health, erosion of cultural values), may arise inside or outside the hazard-hit zone, and often occur with a time-lag. Again, risk characterisation here needs to consider dynamic exposure and vulnerability in multi-hazard contexts. As with direct risk, the definition of indirect-risk metrics is central; for instance, supply-chain disruption costs or reductions in purchasing power.

step 4: Evaluation of direct and indirect risk

Having completed risk identification (step 1) and risk analysis (steps 2–3), the framework proceeds to risk evaluation. In this step, based on risk evaluation, the direct and indirect risks which need to be managed are selected. This phase supports decision-making processes, as limited budgets and mandates, together with possible multiple competing priorities, mean not every direct or indirect risk can be addressed. Together with stakeholders, a set of pre-agreed criteria is applied (e.g., based on cost, policy fit, legal constraints) to separate tolerable risks (e.g., those already insured) from those that still require management and further attention.

step 5: Defining risk management options

Building on the evaluation results (step 4) and earlier analysis (step 1-3), step 5 includes selection of possible risk management options. There is a wide range of possible options available; for instance, options can be structural and non-structural (e.g., policies, zoning, early-warning systems). Risk management options need to be selected in collaboration with stakeholders, depending on, for instance, the risk metrics. Selected options should cover short, medium-, and long-term horizons. In the context of multi-hazard settings, it is especially important to assess synergies and asynergies across options for different hazards. In other words, it is important to consider whether options that address one hazard have any synergies and trade-offs for other hazards.

step 6: Accounting for future systems state

This step considers changes to risk components due to larger processes (e.g., climate, demographic, political, and land use change) as well as due to changes in the system introduced through risk management options discussed in step 5 (e.g., risk management is more recently discussed as one of the risk components (Simpson et al., 2021)). Given the effects of these processes, the system itself will change (e.g., the number or condition of the elements at risk or the system boundaries) and the direct and indirect risks it is exposed to need to be evaluated again. Additionally, one needs to consider how proposed risk management options will perform in the future system state and make adjustments accordingly.

2.2. Guidance protocols

Guidance protocols that accompany the framework are developed with the idea to guide the framework user during the implementation of the framework. It is important to note that the framework is not intended as a process for applying pre-described methods, tools, and approaches as one cannot assume a panacea in the form of a single approach; rather, one must adopt a toolbox-based approach that addresses different needs and can be useful on a case-by-case basis. Therefore, guidance protocols are not designed to offer specifics of how the framework should be implemented; they rather offer a series of broader questions one needs to take into account when working through the framework.

3. Updates over the project period

During the project’s run time, the MYRIAD-EU framework for multi-hazard, multi-sector, systemic risk management and the accompanying guidance protocol were updated several times. The major steps in this development process are outlined in this section and a timeline of the co-development process is provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2 The timeline and major steps in the co-development process of the MYRIAD-EU framework for multi-hazard, multi-sector, systemic risk management and the accompanying guidance protocol.

The development of the MYRIAD-EU framework and guidance protocols followed an iterative, feedback-driven process, marked by two workshops with external stakeholders, two surveys that facilitated pilot’s feedback, and a focus group discussion with pilots leads, all of which shaped the structure and usability of the framework and guidance protocols. Throughout the project, several update documents tracked this process.

3.1. Update of the MYRIAD-EU framework for multi-hazard, multi-sector, systemic risk management

The first draft of the framework was finalized using input by other work packages and presented at the workshop of WP 1 and 2 in month 7 of the project (Figure 2). The insights gathered in this workshop were used to develop the initial framework (D2.1, month 12). The initial round of workshops was held in spring 2022 (MS11, see Figure 2), during which the framework was first presented to external experts and MYRIAD-EU partners and which aimed at gathering feedback on the then-current version of the framework (Figure 3). The feedback was largely positive, particularly appreciating the framework’s clear, stepwise structure and its flexibility to accommodate a range of risk types—from individual to systemic—and incorporate both direct and indirect risks. The emphasis on stakeholder engagement and policy relevance was also well received.

Figure 3 Original design of the MYRIAD-EU framework for individual, multi- and systemic risk analysis, and management

However, several areas for improvement were identified, most notably regarding the practical implementation of the framework. Participants highlighted the need for clearer, step-specific guidance, including best practices and a clearer definition of stakeholder roles at each stage. Additionally, they called for stronger integration of diverse perspectives across system levels (e.g., bottom-up vs. top-down approaches), better handling of uncertainties in multi-risk assessments (e.g., modeling complexities, data availability), and clearer instructions on how to embed existing tools and methods into the framework. These insights led to several concrete revisions: the accompanying guidance protocols were updated based on ongoing research and pilot project experiences, and more attention was given to the consistent use of terminology throughout the framework. Other specific changes included clarifying system challenges and desired states in step 1, initiating discussions on potential risk management options earlier in the process, improving the description of interactions between steps, revising language to be more inclusive (e.g., using “urban change” instead of “urban growth”), and aligning the framework with established risk assessment stages, such as those outlined by Poljansek et al. (2019).

By December 2022, these revisions had been implemented into a new version of the framework, presented in Milestone 3.1 (Figure 1). While the core six-step structure remained intact, the framework had undergone some conceptual as well as considerable visual and refinements. Systems thinking was even more foregrounded in the framework, especially the concepts of system boundaries, system elements, and dependencies. Despite these improvements, feedback indicated that the framework was still seen as highly complex and difficult to understand, especially for stakeholders and pilots.

In response to these concerns, the MYRIAD-EU WP2 team developed a presentation to explain the framework’s concepts and practical value more clearly. This was achieved by using simplified language and plenty of visuals and graphics to relate the complex concepts of system boundaries, system elements, and dependencies. This presentation aimed to answer fundamental questions: why a new approach to risk assessment and management is necessary, what such an approach requires, how the MYRIAD-EU framework differs from traditional models, and how its key systems-based concepts play out across the six steps. As part of this effort, new graphics were created to illustrate the ideas of “systems,” “system elements,” and “system of systems,” (Figure 4) while existing visualizations of “dependencies” and hazard interrelationships were revised (Figure 5). These visuals proved effective in aiding understanding and were redesigned in the MYRIAD-EU style by the project partner Arctik.

KEY CONCEPT

What is a system and what are system elements?

What are systems of systems?

The **Government is a system (1)** which includes **all households (system 3)** as well as the **insurance company (system 2)** which, in turn, includes a part of **all households (system 3)**

Figure 4 The revised graphic explaining the concepts of “systems,” “system elements,” and “system of systems”.

Figure 5 Representation of the interrelationship between hazards (lower part of the figure) and how risks can spread and affect elements of various systems due to dependency (upper part of the figure).

Further feedback for the framework was gathered from pilot leads and was presented in Milestone MS16 (month 43, see Figure 2). This milestone focused on reporting the outcomes of the second and final workshop held in each pilot, which aimed to present and discuss the developed forward-looking disaster risk management (DRM) pathways as well as elicit stakeholders' feedback on the overall project and its outcomes. Milestone MS16 then merged stakeholders' feedback as well as the pilot leads' experiences of applying the framework in their respective contexts. The feedback in MS16 was not substantive but provided valuable indications of engagement and alignment nonetheless.

To further support the refinement of the framework and its guidance protocols, one last feedback collection process was conducted from March to May 2025 (month 43-45). A final questionnaire was distributed to pilot leads in March 2025, structured around the guiding questions for each step of the framework. Its objective was to assess the practical usefulness of these questions and to identify which tools or methods were actually implemented. In May 2025, a final online focus group discussion was held with all pilot leads. This session provided valuable qualitative input, shedding light on experiences with applying the framework, the utility of the guidance protocols, and eliciting additional insights not captured in the survey. It also facilitated reflection on key challenges, perceived usefulness, and opportunities for broader adoption and scaling. The latest update of the framework and guidance protocols, incorporating feedback from Pilot Workshop 2 with MYRIAD-EU partners and stakeholders, as well as the findings from the final survey with pilot leads and the focus group discussion with pilot leads, is presented in section 5 of this deliverable. Refer to Appendix II to find an overview of comments and feedback from pilots concerning the framework (and guidance protocols) throughout the project and via the final survey. The table also details the changes made based on this feedback.

3.2 Update of the guidance protocol

The guidance protocols' initial version was published in D2.1., together with the initial version of the framework in month 12 of the project (see Figure 2). The first update to the guidance protocols was presented in MS7 in February 2023 (Guidance protocols updated (v2) and made available to Pilots). This version marked the first update of the guidance protocols and reflected early-stage feedback and practical alignment with pilot activities. The second update followed in MS8 in March 2024 (Guidance protocols updated (v3) and shared with Pilots). This update incorporated insights from a structured questionnaire and focus group discussions, as reported in milestone MS13. The feedback helped refine both the structure and thematic clarity of the protocols. In November 2024 followed the third update of the guidance protocols as presented in MS9 (Guidance protocols updated (v4) and circulated to Pilots). This version was based on in-depth feedback received during pilot presentations at the MYRIAD-EU General Assembly held in May 2024 in the Canary Islands, as well as additional reporting submitted in D3.3b.

In what follows, the updating process of the guidance protocols of the project runtime is described. Overall, the guidance protocols improved in clarity, expanded focus areas, and incorporated a more structured approach to multi-hazard, multi-risk analysis. No thematic content was explicitly dropped between versions. Instead, the changes reflect elaboration and restructuring rather than omission and were implemented according to pilot input and stakeholder feedback.

Initially, the first version served as a foundational template with broad, open-ended guiding questions for each step of the six-step risk framework. Questions were largely exploratory in tone and offered limited structure for practical implementation. By the second milestone, after both pilots and stakeholders had become more familiar with the framework and applying it in the respective regions, the protocols had undergone significant improvements with respect to structure and content. The questions were made more specific and context-aware. For example, the revised step 1 added clearer sub-themes such as system interconnectivity, governance landscapes, and sector-specific visions: questions now address not only the "what" but also the "why" and "how" – emphasizing planning implications and strategic relevance. Additionally, boxes were added with examples of what information the questions in the guidance protocols could elicit at each step of the framework using a fictional multi-hazard event in the Danube Region as a foil (see Figure 6). Also, the revised guidance protocols include clear distinctions between types of impacts or processes (e.g., tangible vs. intangible impacts, plausible future events in the absence of historical data). Both of the above offers future users of the framework and guidance protocols a practical lens for how to apply the framework in real-world settings.

Step 1: Example Danube Region

- We define our system at the **Danube Region level** (EUSDR definition) and at the **country levels**
- We **exclude** local level and small-scale
- **Sustainability challenge**: spillover effects across Danube countries
- Our focus is on sectors of **agriculture and food, infrastructure and transport, and finance**
- **Hazards of interest**: floods, droughts, heatwaves, wildfires, earthquakes, landslides
- **Multi-hazard scenario** of interest:

There was a severe drought in the Danube Region (e.g., like the 2015 or 2022 drought) that left severe consequences across sectors. After several months, the region is hit by a severe flood (e.g., like the 2006 flood) causing severe loss and damage.

- Examples of **exposure**: population density, area of agricultural lands, number of insured households, critical infrastructure in flood prone areas
- Examples of **vulnerability**: structural vulnerability of road network, agriculture in GDP proportion, net income per capita

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Reducing risks together

Figure 6 Box showing step 1 of the framework applied in the Danube Region and for a fictional multi-hazard event.

Particularly in steps 2 and 3, the updates to the guidance protocols emphasize how risk evolves over time in multi-hazard scenarios. In the updated version, there is a new focus on dynamic exposure and vulnerability – a recognition of cascading and compounding effects over time, which was only briefly mentioned in the original version. Also, the later versions add a more pronounced focus on policy constraints and opportunities. step 1 now explicitly addresses how governance boundaries influence system definitions, while step 4 includes discussion on legal responsibilities and trade-offs (e.g., cost-benefit evaluations and co-benefits).

The updated protocols include more practical considerations on how to structure engagement and integrate stakeholders into decision-making. This builds on the numerous stakeholder interactions the pilots had in the course of the project and focuses strongly on choosing appropriate communication formats for risk results.

Lastly, later versions of the guidance protocols cross-reference supporting deliverables, reports and tools that are outcomes of the MYRIAD-EU project, which makes it easier for users to operationalize the guidance with available resources.

The feedback for the final update of the guidance protocols was gathered in March 2025 via a survey whose aim was to gather feedback on how helpful the questions were in practice and which tools or methods pilots implemented in each step (see Figure 2). In May 2025, a final online focus group discussion was conducted with all pilot leads. This session provided valuable qualitative input, especially regarding experiences with implementing the framework and using the guidance protocols. During the focus groups, additional feedback surfaced that had not been captured by the survey and included reflections on the challenges, usefulness, and opportunities for scaling the framework. Input from both the survey and the Focus Group Discussion resulted in substantial refinement of the guidance protocols (refer to chapter 5 of this document for a more detailed description of the update). Appendix II provides a table of comments and feedback from pilots concerning the guidance protocols throughout the project as well as through the final survey and the changes made based on these comments.

4. Results from project documents, survey and Focus Group Discussion with pilot leads

4.1. Feedback from the project documents

An analysis was conducted of all relevant milestones, deliverables, and presentations produced throughout the project in which pilot leads reported on their application of the framework and provided feedback to WP2. The following chapter presents this analysis in detail, including a table summarising the key documents reviewed (see Table 1).

Across the different pilots and over the years, the MYRIAD-EU framework and its associated guidance protocols received mixed but constructive feedback. As mentioned in the previous section, a recurring theme was the complexity of the framework, especially in its initial versions, which often required that pilot leads have multiple interactions with the WP2 lead (IIASA) to fully understand the underlying concepts of the framework and how the framework can be implemented (for more detailed information on the feedback we refer to D3.3a). Although the complexity was noted as a barrier—highlighted also by requests for a simplified elaboration of the framework (see MS7)—the framework was simultaneously appreciated for its comprehensiveness. Its attention to multi-risk analysis, systemic perspectives, and the distinction between direct and indirect effects, as well as transboundary impacts, was found to be useful (see D3.3a, p.111).

Table 1 Table of deliverables and milestones analyzed for feedback on the MYRIAD-EU framework and its associated guidance protocols. Note: Not all deliverables and/or milestones listed in this table are publicly accessible.

Milestone/ Deliverable	Title
D3.2 a	Detailed annual work-plan for each Pilot (M7-24)
D3.2b	Detailed annual work-plan for each Pilot (M25-36)
D3.2c	Detailed annual work-plan for each Pilot (M37-48)
D3.3a	Interim report on implementation and testing of MYRIAD-EU methods and tools in each Pilot
D3.3b	Interim report on implementation and testing of MYRIAD-EU methods and tools in each Pilot
MS7	Guidance protocols updated (v2) and available to Pilots
MS8	Guidance protocols updated (v3) and available Pilots and available to pilots
MS9	Guidance protocol updated (v4) and available to Pilots
MS11	Pilot Workshop 1 completed and feedback to WP2, 4 6
MS13	Focus Group 1 completed and feedback to WP2, 4-6
MS14	Focus Group 2 completed and feedback to WP2, 4-6
MS16	Pilot Workshop 2 completed and feedback to WP2, 4-6
Veneto GA4 PPT	Pilot update presentation during the GA4
Danube GA4 PPT	Pilot update presentation during the GA5
Canary GA4 PPT	Pilot update presentation during the GA6
North Sea GA4 PPT	Pilot update presentation during the GA7
Scandinavia GA4 PPT	Pilot update presentation during the GA8

The stakeholder engagement dimension was another key point: pilots recommended involving a broader range of stakeholders, including responders and practitioners (D3.3a, p.112), and noted that the consequences of mitigation measures on ecosystems should be explicitly addressed. Some pilots (Veneto and Danube) emphasized that while the concepts were clear and the implementation feasible, a great deal of time was spent translating the material for stakeholder understanding, indicating a need for clearer language and illustrative examples (3.1 Workshop 1, pp. 26, 31).

Aesthetics and accessibility also played a role in stakeholder interaction: while the guidance protocols were generally seen as helpful, stakeholders—particularly in the Scandinavia pilot — found them to be dense in information, and suggested they could benefit from more engaging visuals (3.1 Workshop 1, p.17). Suggestions included incorporating real-life cases, example answers to guiding questions, and simple presentations to support understanding and use in practice (3.1 Workshop 1, p.26).

From an operational perspective, pilots like North Sea and Danube found the protocols practically useful, e.g., for structuring stakeholder workshops and aligning workshop aims (3.1 Workshop 1, p.35). The stepwise structure of the framework was praised for providing a clear and iterative process to manage multi-hazard risks (3.6 Pilot Workshop 2), especially noted by the North Sea pilot, which frequently revisited previous steps in an evolving process.

Lastly, while stakeholder interest in the framework was confirmed in Norway (3.3 Focus Group 1), the Canary Islands pilot reported difficulties in communicating the conceptual framework effectively to stakeholders (3.1 Workshop 1, p.39). Some pilots, such as Veneto, valued the regional

scale application of the framework, which allowed addressing multiple interdependent issues simultaneously (3.1 Workshop 1, p.23).

4.2. Feedback from survey shared with pilot leads

The following section presents the results of the survey sent out in March 2025 to gather the final round of feedback from pilot leads for the last update of the framework and guidance protocols. The survey was sent out to pilot leads as a google form which means that WP2 received one feedback per pilot. The survey asked for overall feedback regarding the framework and guidance protocols (e.g. the overall experience of implementing it, the extent of its implementations, which steps proved most challenging, ...) as well as concrete feedback to the guidance protocol and examples of the tools, methods and approaches applied in each step. A summary of the feedback from the pilot leads is presented below, with related questions grouped together.

How would you describe your overall experience implementing the framework in your pilot? Please reflect on both the benefits and the challenges you encountered. To what extent did the framework guide the work in your pilot? Please elaborate.

Figure 7 gives an overview of the major challenges (blue) and benefits (yellow) reported on by the stakeholders as well as the emerging values (pink) that we could identify from their responses. The experience of implementation of the MYRIAD framework across the five pilot regions (i.e., Scandinavia, North Sea, Canary Islands, Danube, and Veneto) revealed a generally positive reception, with an emphasised benefit of its structured and stepwise design. Pilots emphasised how the framework helped clarify the complexity of multi-hazard and multi-risk. The Scandinavia pilot noted that the framework helped "understand the multiple aspects you have to consider when working on climate risks." At the same time, the North Sea pilot found it useful for "structuring stakeholder inputs and formulating findings." This structured guidance allowed pilots to break down the inherent complexity of multi-(hazard) risk into more manageable stages.

An especially strong aspect of the framework was its support for holistic understanding of the DM process and systems thinking. The pilots valued how it encouraged them to think in interconnected ways about hazards, risks, and different sectors. For instance, the Scandinavia pilot used the framework to identify that water-related risks were central to their context and to clarify whether national or local-level stakeholders were more appropriate to engage. Similarly, the Veneto pilot found the framework helpful in developing a conceptual model that tied together diverse risk analyses (e.g., multi-hazard analysis, multi-risk analysis, DRM pathways), enabling a more comprehensive understanding of disaster risk management in the Veneto region.

Furthermore, pilots emphasised that the framework facilitated more effective engagement with stakeholders, a benefit particularly emphasised by the Canary Islands and North Sea pilots. In the Canary Islands pilot, introducing the framework to stakeholders during Workshop 1 had a dual function: it helped stakeholders understand the challenges, and it forced the pilots to internalise the framework's structure more deeply. They referred to the framework as a "shared reference point," which helped bridge communication between technical and non-technical audiences. This effect was echoed by the North Sea pilot, who appreciated the framework's role in guiding their stakeholder dialogues.

Flexibility was another frequently cited strength of the framework. The framework was not perceived as prescriptive, which allowed pilots to adapt it to their regional contexts, tools, and capacities. In the survey result for the Danube pilot highlighted that the framework "does not require a user to focus on a pre-determined set of methodologies," which allowed for the room to

experiment and iterate. This adaptability was especially appreciated given the complexity of the contexts in which pilots operated (e.g., 14 countries covered by the Danube pilot). It allowed each pilot to interpret the framework in a way that matched their pilot setting, including data availability and pilot-specific challenges.

Despite these identified benefits of the framework, several critical challenges emerged. Some pilots struggled with the conceptual and practical difficulty of “step 1: System Definition.” The Canary Islands pilot described this step as “*highly ambiguous*,” and that the example provided in the guidance protocols was too specific to be transferable. The Danube pilot emphasised that defining the system required conscious decisions about what to exclude from the analysis.

Furthermore, another issue was the iterative and non-linear nature of framework implementation. As pilots advanced through the process of framework implementation, they frequently found themselves having to revisit earlier steps to revise their understanding or adjust inputs. This was described by the Canary Islands pilot as a “*roadmap*” that required constant reinterpretation, and the Danube pilot confirmed that “*the actual implementation of the steps then becomes an iterative process depending on what kind of data can be gathered.*” While this flexibility was useful, it also made the process more challenging and resource-intensive.

The most significant barrier identified was the misalignment between the framework and the tools developed in the MYRIAD-EU project. Although the framework is not intended to prescribe specific tools, pilots found that tools like DAPP-MR and Storylines, or the multi-risk assessment software in WP5, could have been more clearly linked to the framework’s six-step structure. This led to what the Canary Islands pilot called a “*fragmented experience*” and what the Veneto pilot referred to as “*moderate use*” of the framework. This disconnect possibly influenced the implementation and highlighted the need for earlier integration and coordination across scientific work packages and WP2.

Despite these limitations, the pilots found substantial emergent value in the framework. It helped raise awareness of systemic and cascading risks, issues that might otherwise have remained unaddressed. For example, the Danube pilot emphasised its focus on indirect and spill-over risks, which are heavily featured in the framework but are heavily overlooked in most other approaches. Several pilots, including the Scandinavia pilot, also noted that the framework helped them identify key stakeholders to engage in the pilot work. It was recognised that the framework functioned as a useful catalyst for initiating new ways of thinking about multi-hazards and multi-hazard risks.

Figure 7 Graphical representation of the answers to the question on benefits and challenges encountered

What are the key insights from your pilot implementation that could inform the further development and refinement of the framework? In other words, what recommendations would you make regarding its theoretical foundations or the selection and design?

(i) Stronger conceptual and methodological support

Figure 8 gives an overview of the themes and sub-themes identified in the survey as to how to further improve the framework. For instance, across the five pilot sites, one of the most prominent insights was that certain steps of the framework require stronger conceptual and methodological support, particularly step 1 (Finding a System Definition), step 4 (Risk Evaluation), and step 6 (Accounting for Future System States). The Canary Islands pilot emphasised that step 1 needs “*more structure,*” recommending that it include methods for defining system boundaries and understanding sectoral interdependencies. They also highlighted the need for more examples to guide pilots in adapting the framework to their local context. Similarly, the Danube pilot pointed out that step 4, dealing with risk evaluation, remains vague and that more precise definitions of indirect risk metrics would enhance its usefulness.

The Scandinavia and the Danube pilots also raised points about the framing of step 6, which is currently positioned as the final phase of the process. Both pilots emphasised that step 6 should not be interpreted as the end of a linear progression, but rather as a transition into a new cycle of iterative analysis and refinement. The Scandinavian pilot emphasised: “*Getting to step 6 is not necessarily the end.*” This points to a broader need to further emphasise the iterative nature of the framework.

(ii) Enhanced practical application of the framework

The pilots also offered recommendations for enhancing the practical usability of the framework. The Canary Islands pilot suggested that each step should be accompanied by a short, practical guide containing recommended questions to ask, data needs, and methodological options. They stressed that this kind of support would be particularly useful for teams without extensive expertise in disaster risk management. Similarly, the Danube pilot recommended linking each step more explicitly to project deliverables and milestones, which would help ground the framework and connect it more explicitly to scientific work packages (i.e., WP4, 5, and 6). Similarly, the Canary Island pilot called for a tool-step mapping guide. They noted that during their pilot, the MYRIAD-EU tools (e.g., DAPP-MR, Storylines, software) were developed by different work packages, and at times a clear alignment to the framework steps was missing. Providing a simple mapping of which tools are best suited for each step could create much-needed coherence and usability across pilots.

(iii) Greater emphasis on the iterative nature of the framework

Another key insight from several pilots (e.g., Canary Islands, Danube, and Veneto) was that iteration is an inherent part of the process. For example, the Canary Islands pilot reported frequently going “back and forth between defining the system and adjusting risk evaluations.” This observation was echoed by the Veneto pilot, who suggested formal mechanisms that allow users to revisit earlier steps, especially step 1, as new insights emerge through the implementation of subsequent steps and stakeholder engagement. Therefore, making its iterative nature explicit could improve its applicability.

Furthermore, a need to bridge technical analysis with stakeholder engagement was emphasised by the Canary Islands pilot. They stressed that further guidance is needed on how to integrate local knowledge (e.g., when co-developing system definitions with diverse stakeholders).

(iv) Integration of DRM Pathways within the framework

The Veneto pilot proposed a more conceptual enhancement: integrating the development of Disaster Risk Management (DRM) pathways as a formal part of the framework. They noted that while the current structure ends with an evaluation of future risk states, it stops short of linking multi-risk assessment with concrete planning or decision-making processes, supported by tools such as DAPP-MR.

Overall, the pilots collectively reinforced that the theoretical foundation of the framework is strong, but its usability could be further enhanced. Priorities for refinement include enhancing methodological clarity (especially in steps 1, 4, and 6), better integrating tools developed within MYRIAD-EU, acknowledging the iterative nature of the framework, and strengthening guidance on stakeholder engagement.

Figure 8 Summary of identified improvements for the framework based on survey responses.

Sub-themes (light blue) are organized into clusters of overarching themes (dark blue).

Which steps of the framework did you find most challenging to implement, and why? Which steps of the framework did you find easiest to implement, and why?

Step 1 (Finding a System Definition) was seen as the easiest step to implement. The Veneto, Danube, and North Sea pilots found it manageable due to strong pre-existing data, conceptual clarity, or the support of stakeholders. The Danube pilot especially appreciated how the framework's conceptual background in systems thinking helped them frame their regional analysis within larger governance structures (i.e., system of systems approach), suggesting that the framework's theoretical underpinning was effective here.

Across the pilots, step 4 (Risk Evaluation) emerged as the most widely acknowledged challenge, particularly when it came to dealing with indirect risks. Both the Danube and Veneto pilot found this step difficult due to the spatial scale of analysis (Danube), the cross-sectoral nature of risk, and the lack of concrete metrics or data. For example, the Veneto pilot relied on stakeholder interviews and focus group discussions for the qualitative assessments and combined this approach with AI tools to determine when actions are needed for various coastal hazards. This combination of tools highlights the step's methodological demands, especially in the context of establishing quantitative thresholds. Interestingly, the Scandinavia pilot considered step 4 to be the easiest, even though others found it the most challenging. Their experience shows how internal capacity and existing tools, like the GRACE model in the Scandinavia pilot, can significantly reduce barriers in what is otherwise a complex and resource-intensive stage. This discrepancy suggests that step 4's difficulty is highly context-dependent.

Step 5 (Management Options) was flagged as particularly challenging by the Scandinavia pilot, mainly because it depends heavily on engagement with decision-makers who possess crucial contextual knowledge. They also emphasised that the sheer number of possible options, especially at the national scale, can be overwhelming.

The Canary Islands pilot pointed out that the greatest difficulty lies in the integration and interconnection of all steps. This cross-cutting challenge reflects the complexity of conducting multi-hazard and multi-sectoral risk assessment.

What changes would you recommend for a revised version of the framework? Please explain what changes you suggest, why they are needed, and how they could improve the framework.

One of the areas identified for improvement was step 5 (Defining Risk Management Options), which was seen as too broad. The Scandinavia pilot proposed breaking this step down into smaller, more manageable sub-steps. Subdividing the step could improve usability by providing a more stepwise process for the identification of risk management options.

A major cross-cutting theme was the need to strengthen the guidance protocols, particularly by including more context-specific examples based on pilots, as suggested by the Canary Islands pilot and Danube pilots. The Canary Islands pilot noted that having worked examples would have helped clarify the application of each step, while the Danube pilot saw this as a key area where the guidance could evolve, even if the framework's structure remained unchanged.

The Canary Islands pilot suggested that closer facilitation and hands-on support during the implementation phase would have been highly beneficial. They reflected that more pilot-specific facilitation might have helped surface implementation issues earlier and allowed for adaptive problem-solving.

In terms of tools, multiple pilots called for better integration and clearer connections between the framework and tools developed within MYRIAD-EU. The North Sea pilot emphasised that it took significant effort to understand how the framework related to the DAPP-MR approach. The Veneto pilot recommended the development of a comprehensive toolbox or handbook that includes not just MYRIAD-developed tools but also useful external methods, datasets, and practices. Veneto also suggested linking the framework with broader disaster risk management (DRM) frameworks.

As stated before, several pilots, particularly the Veneto pilot, underscored the importance of enabling iteration and feedback loops within the framework. They suggested the framework should include explicit mechanisms for returning to earlier steps (especially step 1, finding a system definition) when new information or conditions emerge.

Finally, a key recommendation from the Veneto pilot was the inclusion of DRM pathways as a formal part of the framework. This addition could support users in translating multi-(hazard) risk analysis into decision-making and planning.

Based on your experience, what advice or recommendations would you give to future users of the framework?

One of the strongest messages for future users from the pilots who were testing the framework in practice for future users is to embrace the iterative nature of the framework. Both Scandinavia and the Danube pilot emphasised that the process would involve revisiting earlier steps multiple times, and that this should not be viewed as a failure of planning, but rather a strength of the approach. This iterative dynamic allows for the integration of new insights, shifts in understanding, and adaptations as the process unfolds.

Alongside this, the Danube pilot advised users to be open-minded and experimental when selecting tools and methods. Instead of rigidly choosing a method at the outset, teams should stay flexible and allow the needs of each step and the evolving understanding of the system to inform the choice of approaches. They also highlighted the framework's value as a co-development tool that can bridge knowledge and perspectives across sectors, governance levels, and disciplines.

The North Sea pilot also pointed out that successful framework implementation also depends on the readiness and awareness of the users themselves. Without sufficient understanding of the system's complexity or a willingness to embrace uncertainty, the process can become very complex.

The Veneto pilot provided two key recommendations: first, that teams should combine qualitative and quantitative tools to better capture the multifaceted nature of risk; and second, that stakeholders must be engaged early and continuously. They noted that involving relevant stakeholders from the beginning through to the end of the process can enhance the legitimacy of the framework. Stakeholder involvement helped ground the analysis in local realities and supported the translation of results into actionable strategies.

Feedback specific to guidance protocols

Figure 9 Pilots' use of the framework as per survey answers

Out of five pilots, two (Scandinavia, Canary Islands) indicated they have used the protocols extensively, one (Danube) regularly, and two (North Sea, Veneto) occasionally (see figure 9). Heavy users praised the structure for framing research and stakeholder dialogue; light users found the protocols helpful at start-up but noted that as the research progressed, they were used less extensively as tools and methods were applied to regional contexts rather than a strict adherence to a fixed protocol. Specific examples of the application of the guidance protocols for each pilot include:

- The Scandinavia pilot indicated that guidance protocols were a key for research design and for framing stakeholder interactions.
- The North Sea pilot used the protocols mainly in early preparation for stakeholder engagement.
- The Canary Islands pilot used the protocols throughout the project but indicated misalignment with pilot-specific tools.
- The Danube pilot indicated a regular use of guidance protocols and a frequent cross-check to ensure all framework aspects were covered.
- The Veneto pilot used the protocols selectively and indicated the evolving nature of the pilot work which was not always aligned with protocols.

The common strength identified for the guidance protocols was a clear stepwise structure and questions which were seen as helpful, for instance, in engaging stakeholders.

Pilots provided detailed suggestions on the guidance for each of the steps (table 2).

Table 2 Suggestions for improvement of guidance for each of the steps

Pilot	Scandinavia	North Sea	Canary Islands	Danube	Veneto
Step 1			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More examples needed 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inclusion of hazards other than natural clear identification of stakeholders and their roles Dependencies of system on broader contexts
Step 2					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reconsider the term "system owner" Inclusion of spatial dynamics of risk
Step 3			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> definition of interdependencies among sectors and elements 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> link between direct and indirect risks Reconsider the term "system owner" dynamic feedback and interdependencies
Step 4				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> more examples from the pilots 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> communication strategies for risks clearer criteria for risk selection
Step 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> having subgroups of questions 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> identification of feasibility of risk reduction measures
Step 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> integration of different timelines for different sectors 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> further guidance needed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> clearly bring in changes brought by risk management options 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> more guidance on how to integrate evolving uncertainties

4.3 Feedback from the follow-up focus group discussion

Similar to the results of the survey, presented above, in the following discussion pilots appreciated the six-step structure and emphasized that this helped with converting an otherwise very complex multi-hazard assessment challenge into a series of steps. This structure also helped communicate the complex challenge with stakeholders who were not necessarily always familiar with multi-hazard aspects.

The framework was also appreciated for promoting systems thinking and seen as providing a holistic understanding of interactions across hazards, sectors and governance levels. This was recognized as an important advancement from the prevalent practice of focusing on single hazards or in best case, multiple single hazards rather than interconnected hazards. For instance, the Veneto pilot reported that the framework served to integrate separate but unlinked analysis, such as multi-hazard mapping, socio-economic exposure metrics and DRM pathways into a coherent process.

The absence of prescriptive methodological requirements was seen as a strength. However, this flexibility was also seen as a challenge at the same time, as it meant that pilots had to spend considerable time and resources to draw the boundaries of their analysis and connect everything to a coherent workflow.

The graphical representation of the framework facilitated dialogue with non-technical stakeholders, which was seen as a strength. Nevertheless, baseline knowledge in multi-hazard risk concepts diverged markedly. The North Sea pilot indicated that stakeholder discussions initially required reducing the complexity through detailed explanations.

A strong suggestion for further framework development coming out of the focus group was a tiered engagement model with the framework that would offer basic, intermediate and advanced entry pathways, depending on the user of the framework, their previous knowledge and capacity. The first tier could be based on using qualitative approaches to build understanding, while the intermediate would be based on semi-quantitative approaches. On the other hand, the advanced tier could incorporate full quantitative analysis, e.g., disaster risk management pathways modelling.

Pilots reported an initial “*period of complexity*” while pilots internalized new terminology introduced by the framework, its underlying concepts, and considered data requirements. Several pilots observed that the iterative logic of the framework is not adequately reiterated, despite explanatory notes in the framework description and guidance protocols. To this end, a proposal was made to include prompts throughout the framework that would emphasize its iterative nature and “*feedback loops*”.

Similar to the survey, pilots expressed concern about misalignment between the framework and tools, methods and approaches coming from WP4, 5 and 6. For instance, the Canary Islands and Scandinavia pilot mentioned how tools developed for pathways and storylines were not always easily comparable or able to be incorporated in the six steps of the framework. Participants also interpreted this misalignment as a coordination issue rather than a conceptual flaw of the framework. They asked for a detailed mapping of how tools developed within MYRIAD-EU map against different framework steps.

Acquiring appropriate data was also recognized as a cross-cutting challenge. Even in pilots that were seen as more “data-rich”, such as the Scandinavia pilot, it was reported that they struggled at times with which data was needed or where to find it (e.g., for indirect impact assessment).

Another aspect raised was a general background of those implementing the framework. For instance, physical scientists reported limited experience with interviews and workshops. The framework’s interdisciplinarity was therefore regarded as both an asset and a capacity burden. Similar points were raised in relation to the background of stakeholders implementing the framework. Pilots reasoned that in cases where stakeholders had strong technical backgrounds and understanding of disaster and climate risk, the process of implementing the framework might have been smoother (at least in the very beginning).

Consensus emerged that effective institutionalization of the framework demands support mechanisms extending beyond typical research project cycles. For instance, the Veneto pilot raised that the stakeholder involvement need to be facilitated if analytical outputs, such as the framework, are to inform regulatory policy making and practice.

5. Approach to the update of the framework and guidance protocols

In Section 4, we presented in detail the feedback from pilot leads to the framework and guidance protocols. As our analysis showed, many benefits and strengths of the previously developed material have been identified. However, pilots provided a number of suggested improvements which will render the framework more usable and useful and further facilitate its implementation.

Overall, the feedback indicated that the framework itself does not require substantial improvements in terms of the structure. The six-steps structure was highly appreciated, and it was also emphasised that the framework itself has already gained traction in the wider scientific community; for instance, according to Google Scholar, the scientific paper presenting the framework (Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2023) has been cited 57 times (on 23 May 2025), including citations in high level documents such as the first European Climate Risk Assessment published in 2024. A clear, stepwise procedure has been praised as very helpful in breaking down a complex phenomenon into a set of manageable steps, while the framework maintained a holistic approach to identifying and tackling multi-hazard and systemic risks.

However, as outlined in Section 4, the pilots have identified a number of areas where the framework can be strengthened. For instance, a call for more examples from the pilots that could aid the implementation of different framework steps; better alignment of tools, methods, and approaches developed within MYRIAD-EU and framework steps; and more emphasis on the iterative nature of the framework. In addition to these more cross-cutting issues, pilots proposed step-specific improvements; for example, more structured guidance to step 5, emphasising that the framework does not “end” with step 6, etc. Taking this valuable feedback into account, it became apparent that the majority of requested changes can be implemented through the improvements to the guidance protocols. This primarily requires adding new information and adding and reorganising the existing guidance questions per step. Some of the major changes (presented in the guidance protocol in Appendix II) are:

- **Overview of tools, methods, and approaches implemented in the pilots:** For each step of the framework, a detailed overview of tools, methods, and approaches implemented in all of the five pilots. This overview directly tackles a concern raised by pilots that there was a need for more concrete examples and guidance on how to implement a specific framework step.
- **Detailed examples from pilots:** In relation to the point above, a detailed example from pilots will be presented in each of the steps. These were previously reported in D3.3b, and are used in the guidance protocols as short and indicative examples, providing a possible user with more detail.
- **Emphasis on the iterative nature of the framework:** The guidance protocols have now been updated with an example of what this iteration can mean after each step of the framework.
- **Disclaimer of the three-tiered approach:** In the discussion following the last survey, a proposal was put forward that guidance protocols would benefit from having a tiered approach that would offer basic, intermediate, and advanced entry pathways. Although a decision was made that a full implementation of this suggestion would require fundamental changes to the guidance protocols and a more detailed analysis (including engagement with possible users for making a value judgement on what should be classified under which entry pathway), the MYRIAD-EU WP2 team has opted to introduce this disclaimer at the very beginning of guidance protocols. This was done to further convey the message that the framework can be implemented with a variety of tools, from qualitative to semi-

quantitative and quantitative tools. In addition, within the dashboard the discussion of each step was structured in a similar way as the three-tiered approach, going from conceptual to more advanced analysis stages.

It is also important to emphasise that although the vast majority of feedback will be incorporated in the guidance protocols, not all of the feedback received could be included. This specifically refers to the following comments:

- **Mapping of tools, methods, and approaches beyond MYRIAD-EU:** A proposal was put forward to also include examples of tools, methods, and approaches beyond those developed in MYRIAD-EU, to depict how different steps of the framework could be implemented. However, this was deemed beyond the scope of the WP2 work, given the focus and the resources available. As continuously reiterated, the framework steps can be implemented using a variety of approaches, and the guidance protocols give examples of those that were implemented in MYRIAD-EU. However, MYRIAD-EU has also developed the Disaster Risk Gateway (https://disasterriskgateway.net/index.php/Main_Page), which serves as an open-access repository for discovery and sharing of approaches for understanding, analysing, and managing multi-hazard and multi-hazard risks. Additionally, we want to refer to the MYRIAD-EU dashboard (<https://dashboard.myriadproject.eu/>) for a detailed description of the framework, how each step was implemented by the pilots as well as which tool and methods were used within each step.
- **Integration challenges between framework development and tools development in WP4, 5, and 6:** pilot leads also emphasised that there could have been a better alignment between the development of the framework and tools, methods, and approaches developed in WP4, 5, and 6. The updated guidance protocols now map out which tools, methods, and approaches were used in each step. A key challenge was the misalignment in timing—while the prototype framework had to be finalised early (by M12), many of the corresponding tools were still under development and only became available at later stages. This temporal disconnect made it difficult to ensure seamless integration. Although links between tools and framework steps were included where possible, the broader question remains of how to structure such processes to allow for better coordination, especially when complex modelling tools require extended development time.
- **Future system states (step 6) and DAPP-MR:** The goal of WP2 was to develop a harmonised framework for multi-hazard, multi-sector, systemic risk management. Future system states came in within step 6 and can be in principle of multiple sorts. The framework was developed to be broad enough to be able to include different analysis of future system states including climate or multi-hazard storyline approaches (Shepherd et al. 2018, van den Hurk et al. 2023, probabilistic assessments using RCPs and SSPs, through Integrated Assessment Models, as well as other modelling approaches see Botzen et al. 2018) and corresponding policy analysis, hybrid approaches and for this project most importantly, Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways for Multi Risks (DAPP-MR, Schlumberger et al. 2022). The full details of the approach can be found in aforementioned paper and are thus omitted here. DAPP-MR begins after step 5 where the risk management and policy strategies were developed for the current system state and policy analysis for future system states using the dynamic adaptive policy pathways approach was applied in a multi-risk context using a three stage process. The information gathered within the previous 5 steps are used as input for these stages and adapted to the DAPP-MR methodology (see D6.3).

6. Conclusion

This deliverable has focused on reporting the experiences of MYRIAD-EU pilots in implementing the MYRIAD-EU framework, and collecting and implementing feedback for the update of the framework and design of the final guidance protocols. It is based on the feedback collected by the pilots and through three lines of evidence: 1) feedback from deliverables and milestones of WP2 and WP3 as well as presentations held at general assemblies, 2) survey with pilot leads from April 2025, and 3) focus group discussion with pilot leads in May 2025. The feedback generally emphasized a positive reception of the framework; however, a number of improvements were identified, which are directly introduced in the guidance protocols outlined in the appendix.

Within the framework development we argued that a systemic perspective is beneficial when it comes to the assessment and management of multi-hazards and multi-risks. We especially argued that setting system boundaries, enabling a system-of-systems approach, as well as focusing on dependencies, either hazard or sectorial wise, enables a way forward on how to deal with multi-(hazard) risks within a step-by-step approach, and therefore providing a frame one can work with. It was already clear at the very beginning of the project that complexity was increasing substantially when multi-hazards as well as multi-risk situations needed to be incorporated. Apart from data and modelling challenges also interactions with stakeholders and making the results useful for them was very resource intensive. This is not in the least due to the fact that the complexities involved had to be reduced to manageable levels—both in terms of modelling, where modellers need to simplify systems enough to build accurate and computationally feasible models, and in terms of stakeholder engagement, where complexity must be broken down to ensure stakeholders can understand the problems at hand without being overwhelmed, thereby enabling meaningful discussion and knowledge co-development. Indeed, the workshop and focus groups within the Pilots using the framework had to bring to “life” the essential features of this new systemic perspective, a task that should not be underestimated and which would need more research to ensure a smooth process from information to action.

The multitude of large scale hazard events, conflicts as well as emergent risks, including pandemics and technological uncertainties, calls for an even greater appreciation of multi-risks contexts and a systemic perspective. How such events are unfolding and influencing disaster and climate related dimensions is a research topic not yet fully tackled and which deserves more attention in the future. Current suggestions such as the triple dividend or multiple dividend approaches are trying to link the disaster and climate risk domain with other systems and therefore providing a new way forward on how to holistically assess different kinds of risks that are inherently interrelated. The MYRIAD-EU framework serves as a stepping stone toward greater integration across different hazards and risks. With the concept of dependency at its core, it offers a way to connect and analyse interactions not only between natural, biological, and technological hazards but also with broader societal dimensions such as wellbeing and health.

Appendix I

Guidance protocols

Guidance protocols that accompany the framework are developed with an idea to guide the framework user during the implementation of multi and systemic risk assessment and management. It is important to note that the framework we present is not intended as a process for applying pre-described methods, tools, and approaches. From the perspective of the framework and science, one cannot assume a panacea in the form of a single approach; rather, one must adopt a toolbox-based approach that addresses different needs and can be useful on a case-by-case basis.

Therefore, guidance protocols are not designed to offer specifics of how the framework should be implemented. They rather offer a series of broader questions one needs to take into account when working through the framework. Therefore, in the following sections, we present some guiding questions. Throughout the lifetime of MYRIAD-EU, these questions were revisited and expanded.

The data needed for the guiding questions below can be obtained through a variety of methods. For example, through stakeholder engagement, secondary research based on literature reviews, national, local and regional loss/impact datasets, and by accessing existing data sources through platforms such as OASIS, risk and hazard viewers like ThinkHazard, EM-DAT and GAR.

One aspect to consider is that the level of the engagement with the framework and guidance protocols depends on multiple aspects, including data availability, technical expertise at hand, time available, and problem under consideration. Therefore, an engagement with the framework in the implementation process can be done through a three-tier approach:

- 1) Entry level: based on qualitative analysis for initial assessment.
- 2) Intermediate level: includes semi-quantitative approaches.
- 3) Advanced level: largely applies advanced quantitative modelling.

It is important to emphasize that, as is the case with the framework, the use of the guidance protocols is **inherently iterative**: users are advised to revisit and revise earlier steps as new insights emerge during the process. This ongoing refinement ensures that each step remains aligned with the evolving understanding of risks, contexts, and interdependencies uncovered in subsequent stages.

Updated guiding questions for step 1: Finding a system definition

The objective of step 1 is to clearly determine the elements within and outside the system, to identify current challenges, explore potential solutions, and discern hazard/multi-hazard scenarios of interest. This includes understanding not only what is within the system but also what is influencing the system from the outside, such as broader policy frameworks or transboundary dependencies.

The boundaries of the system vary depending on who sets these boundaries. For example, a homeowner household considers only its own assets such as its house, an insurer considers only the assets it insures, and a national government considers all the assets of the respective country. In other words, a homeowner may define their system as all the assets they own, an insurer defines their system as all the assets they have insured, while the national government defines their system as all the assets of that country. These system owners operate at different scales (e.g., from a household to a governmental department, which oversees different sectors) and their boundaries

may overlap, be nested, or be influenced by external actors (e.g., EU regulations affecting national or local policies). In what follows, we are using the term "system owner", which can refer to a variety of actors: From impacted sectors, affected communities, relevant institutions, to other stakeholders.

In addition to natural hazards, it is essential to consider anthropogenic (human-induced) hazards such as industrial accidents, pollution, land degradation, and unsustainable development patterns. These can significantly affect exposure, vulnerability, and risk, particularly when interacting with natural hazards (e.g., pollution exacerbating the impacts of floods on ecosystems).

The work done in Work Package 6 on developing the DAPP-MR approach can serve as a valuable guide for Step 1 of our framework. Both approaches begin with identifying the system's boundaries, challenges and opportunities and require its user to explore potential hazard scenarios, relevant objectives, key actors, and uncertainties. Thus, the DAPP-MR

The following are example questions to consider in implementing step 1 of the framework (questions are not in the order of asking nor prescribed but just for the reader's consideration):

Drawing (initial) boundaries of the system

- What is the geographical region you are operating in/have responsibility for?
 - For instance, an insurance company might be operating at a national scale while the local government oversees a certain geographical area (e.g., city boundaries).
- What are the system's administrative, legal, and institutional boundaries?
- What are the boundaries determined by policies and governance you have a responsibility for?
 - For instance, the agricultural department might be interested only in areas of agricultural land use, while the disaster risk management department has a remit of implementing national disaster risk management policies.
- What external or higher-level policies (e.g., national, EU) influence your system? How do these external drivers affect your ability to manage risks locally?
- What are the main elements within the system, and how do they interact?
- Is there any specific sector of particular interest/focus?
- How is the system you are considering interconnected with other systems (e.g., policy networks, economic links, ecosystems, infrastructure)?
- Are there any dependencies or critical inputs from outside your defined system boundaries or outputs across those system boundaries (e.g., supply chains, upstream water sources, ...)?

Challenges and vision for the system

- What is your vision for your system (e.g., for a sector or for local government) and what are your goals? In other words, what is the ideal "destination" or "state" of your system and what are your goals in achieving this?
- What are the current challenges (i.e., sustainability challenges such as spatial planning in the face of disaster risk, the resilience of tourism to multi-risk, ...) you are experiencing in reaching this goal?
- How do natural hazards or anthropogenic (human-induced) hazards relate to these challenges/hinder you in reaching the goal?

- Are there long-term external trends (e.g., urbanization, climate change, demographic shifts, economic pressures) that pose challenges to your system?

Governance landscape and stakeholder analysis

- What are the main policies that are guiding your work? For instance, national disaster risk management policies, local development plans, transportation, and agricultural policies, ...
- How do the main policies guiding your work determine what you can and cannot do in terms of risk management?
- Who are the other main actors you are collaborating with? For instance, the department of finance in a country might collaborate often with the department of agriculture.
- What are these main actors' roles and responsibilities in risk management?
- Who are the decision-makers, implementers, funders, and knowledge holders? What is the balance of power between them?
- Are there any coordination mechanisms or institutional gaps between different actors and levels?

Single and multi-hazards

- What are natural or anthropogenic hazards (or other hazards of interest in your region, such as biological or environmental ones) that impact you and/or your work/mandate/the geographical area you are in charge of? In the case of working in a setting with limited experience of previous natural hazards, ask about plausible future events. Also consider the fact that hazards can be transboundary in nature.
- Do these hazards interrelate in any way? Can you provide some examples? Can you provide examples of cascading or compound risks?
- What hazard scenarios are of interest to you? For instance, if only considering single hazards, it might be frequent and/or more extreme flooding. If considering multi-hazards, it might be different multi-hazard scenarios (e.g., heatwaves increasing the probability of fires or earthquakes triggering landslides).
- How are the goals of sectors in your system impacted by single and multi-hazards?

Exposure and vulnerability

- Thinking of these hazards and the areas they impact, can you identify exposed and vulnerable elements of your system? For instance, insurance companies are insuring households and companies, and the national government is in charge of all members/components of society, therefore these are the elements exposed that will be of interest. For vulnerability, think of it in a broader sense (e.g., the structural vulnerability of buildings, the economic vulnerability of people and companies, socially differentiated vulnerability by age, gender, and economic status).
- Are there vulnerable groups or sectors particularly affected by anthropogenic or multi-hazard risks?
- How do interdependencies within the system create indirect or cascading vulnerabilities?
- If this is a difficult task for you, think of how different scenarios could help you better understand the system's vulnerabilities. In other words, try to think of concrete scenarios that can help you to get a clearer picture of which system elements could be vulnerable.
- Going back to the main elements of the system you identified and the potential interrelationships they might have, can you identify additional exposed and vulnerable elements of your system because of that interrelationship (i.e. system elements, which might not be directly affected by a single- or multi-hazard, but indirectly)?

Risk management

- What do you think is needed to reduce risk in your area/sector?
- Which actors are responsible for implementing risk reduction measures?
- What are the existing risk management options for the hazards of interest? What are good practices in the existing risk management options, and can they be built upon?
- Which management options are missing, and are there gaps? What is needed to fill these gaps?
- What is important to do for risk management in your area/sector/focus, but it is outside of your responsibility? Note: This question might be important for delineating what is outside of the system.
- How are responsibilities shared or contested across actors and scales?

Tools and Methodologies

- Are there any existing frameworks or methodologies you can use to define and analyze your system (e.g., Causal Loop Diagrams, risk matrices,...)?
- Would developing a timeline, matrix or system diagram help you understand the cascading effects of risks across sectors?
- What methods (desk reviews, stakeholder dialogues, workshops, modelling, mapping, ...) could you use to gather information?

Step 1

Fictional example

There was a severe drought in the Rhine Region (e.g., like the 2018 or 2022 drought) that caused significant disruptions across multiple sectors, including navigation, agriculture, and energy production. After several months, the region is struck by a major flood (e.g., similar to the 2021 flood in Western Germany) that results in extensive loss and damage.

Implementation of step 1:

- System: the Rhine Region level and at the national level for involved countries (e.g., Germany, France, Switzerland, the Netherlands, Luxembourg, Austria, Liechtenstein).
- Excluded: local-scale and small-scale assessments.
- Sustainability challenge: spillover effects and transboundary impacts across Rhine basin countries.
- Sectors: agriculture and food, infrastructure and transport, and finance.
- Hazards of interest: floods, droughts, heatwaves, wildfires, landslides, and earthquakes.

Examples from MYRIAD-EU

North Sea Pilot:

Implementation of step 1:

- Used a collaborative systems analysis process with stakeholders from the outset.
- Applied Causal Chains to map system elements and boundaries.
- Defined both geographic and sectoral scope dynamically through stakeholder input.

Danube Pilot:

Implementation of step 1:

- Employed the “system of systems” approach to capture macro-regional complexity (14 countries).
- Incorporated multi-hazard scope: floods, earthquakes, droughts, selected via stakeholder workshop.
- Focused on sectoral interdependencies in agriculture, finance, and navigation.

Table 3 Table listing the tools and/or methods applied per pilot for their implementation of step 1. For further examples of methods, tools and datasets or practices that could be helpful in the implementation of this step, we refer to the Disaster Risk Gateway (https://disasterriskgateway.net/index.php/Main_Page).

Pilot	Tool/method used
Canary Islands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - Desk review - CSAA - Forensic analysis - Stakeholder validation
Danube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CSAA - Stakeholder validation - Desk review

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DPSIR framework - Storylines - DAPP-MR
North Sea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - Desk review - Causal Chains - CSAA
Scandinavia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DAPP-MR - Desk review - Interviews - Storylines
Veneto	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - Desk review - Stakeholder validation - Multi-risk conceptual model - Climate risk indicators

To date, the MYRIAD-EU team produced the following deliverables which can contribute to the operationalization of this step of the framework:

- D1.1 Wiki-style online crowdsourcing platform of multi-hazard, multi-risk methods, models, and tools (Disaster Risk Gateway)
- D1.2 Handbook of multi-hazard, multi-risk concepts, definitions, and indicators
- D1.3 Report on policies, policy-making processes, and governance of multi-hazard, multi-risk management
- D4.2 Guidance on methodology for extracting empirical evidence from pilots
- D5.3: Final report on methods for generating hazard event sets and quantifying risk
- D6.2: Guidance document for Pilots on collaborative systems analysis approaches
- D6.4: Final report on collaborative systems and DAPP
- D6.5 Online repository of storylines on multi-risk decision-making

Updated guiding questions for step 2: Characterization of direct risk

The objective of step 2 is to characterize the direct risk of system elements that have been affected by direct contact with a hazard and to determine direct risk metrics. It should be noted that the affected system elements may be tangible (i.e., physical/touchable) or intangible (i.e., non-material). In addition, impacts can be measured using market-based methods (e.g., monetary values) or other indicators (e.g., non-monetizable values such as loss of life). For instance, a household may be directly affected by flooding as the house and property will be damaged. Another household may be directly affected by earthquakes as the house and property will be damaged. An insurer may be directly affected by both losses due to claim payments. A government will be directly affected by both losses due to infrastructure losses and giving immediate assistance to households as well as in the failure of insurers (e.g., insurers of last resort).

Example questions to consider in step 2 (questions are not in the order of asking nor prescribed, just for the reader's consideration):

Direct impacts

- What are direct impacts that occur due to contact of the system elements with a hazard/multi-hazard event?
 - For instance, from an earthquake: loss of life, destruction of roads and interruption of transportation due to an earthquake, tourism sites affected, etc.
- As mentioned above, think of a variety of direct impacts, and take into account both those that are tangible and intangible. Also, note which can be quantified and expressed in monetary terms and which require alternative metrics (e.g. semi-quantitative or qualitative).
- In some cases, the stakeholders might not have experience with previous events (e.g., due to a lack of historical events). In these cases, work with stakeholders to define direct impacts based on plausible future events (e.g., by using the storylines approach).
- How will you assess these direct risks? You could, for instance, use qualitative methods like interviews or focus groups, or quantitative methods like statistical analysis or machine learning.

Direct risk metrics

- What are the main direct impacts of interest for the system owner (e.g., sectors, institutions, local government)? E.g., the transport sector might be interested in minimizing interruption to the transportation system. What are the metrics for these impacts? For example:
 - Loss of access to health facilities
 - Loss of numbers of fishing and transportation ships
 - Number of displaced people
 - Number of claims filed with insurance
- In the case of working in a setting where historical events are few and/or limited, ask about which metric of direct risk would be of interest for a plausible future event.

Dynamics of exposure, vulnerability, and impacts

- For a multi-hazard scenario and characterization of direct risk, take into account how vulnerability (e.g., physical, social, economic, environmental) and exposure change.
 - For instance, buildings can be structurally weakened by an earthquake and, therefore, are more vulnerable in case of a consecutive earthquake.
- How do people, infrastructure, or ecosystems become newly exposed due to prior hazards?
 - For instance, a population's exposure to floods might change if people are moved to a flood-prone area following a different hazard (e.g., fire).
- If considering a multi-hazard scenario, how do direct impacts appear in time and space as the multi-hazard scenario is progressing? For instance, considering how things change over time: If Hazard X causes a certain direct impact (I1) at an initial moment (t=0), what would be the direct impact (I2) of the same Hazard X at a later point in time (t=1)?

Temporal and Spatial Dynamics

- How do direct impacts vary across space within the system?
 - Consider how geography, land use, or spatial distribution of assets or communities influence direct risk.
 - Are certain areas disproportionately affected or more vulnerable due to their location or connectivity?

- In multi-hazard scenarios, how do impacts interact and progress across time and space?
 - E.g., A fire in area A may alter vegetation and runoff, exacerbating flood risk in downstream area B.

With these new insights gained, make sure to revisit step 1 and adjust your system definition if needed!

Why might that be necessary?

While quantifying direct risk, you may discover that a hazard like flash floods, initially overlooked, is significantly impacting exposed infrastructure. Therefore, you might have to return to **Step 1** to revise the system boundaries or update the list of relevant hazards and exposed elements.

Step 2

Fictional example

Implementation of step 2:

- Road damages due to severe droughts (e.g., cracking)
- Destruction of road infrastructure due to floods
- Loss of navigability on the river due to droughts
- Crop losses
- Damages of properties (households)
- Insurance losses
 - Risk metrics: Annual losses in agricultural production, proportion of insured households experiencing financial losses, days of navigation lost
 - Dynamics of vulnerability and exposure: e.g., road infrastructure weakened by droughts hit by floods.

Examples from MYRIAD-EU

Veneto Pilot:

Implementation of step 2:

- Used qualitative data (interviews, FGDs) and quantitative tools (machine learning).
- Applied DBSCAN (Unsupervised ML) to define historical multi-hazard footprints (1992–2021).
- Developed ML models for vulnerability in ecosystems and river water quality.

Danube Pilot:

Implementation of step 2:

- Used co-production workshops to map key direct risks with stakeholders.
- Developed direct impact scenarios for agent-based models (ABM), especially floods and earthquakes.
- Applied the CatSim tool for probabilistic assessment of fiscal risks due to disasters.

Table 4 Table listing the tools and/or methods applied per pilot for their implementation of step 2. For further examples of methods, tools and datasets or practices that could be helpful in the implementation of this step, we refer to the Disaster Risk Gateway.

Pilot	Tool/method used
Canary Islands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - Desk reviews - Forensic analysis - Dynamic Vulnerability Model (tourism) - Resilient Tourism Scorecard
Danube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CATSIM - ABM - DAPP-MR - Storylines - Stakeholders workshops
North Sea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - Group discussions - Interviews
Scandinavia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GRACE (macroeconomic model) - DAPP-MR - Storylines - Interviews
Veneto	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - Stakeholder interviews - Focus group discussions - Adapted MYRIAD-HESA - ML-based susceptibility mapping - Supervised ML methods

To date, the MYRIAD-EU team produced the following deliverables which can contribute to the operationalization of this step of the framework:

- D1.1 Wiki-style online crowdsourcing platform of multi-hazard, multi-risk methods, models, and tools (Disaster Risk Gateway)
- D4.2 Guidance on methodology for extracting empirical evidence from pilots
- D4.3 Report on novel methods for detecting empirical evidence of dynamics and feedback of risk drivers
- D4.4 Methods for Quantifying the Dynamics and Feedbacks of Multi-Hazard Risk
- D5.2 Interim report on methods for generating hazard event sets and quantifying risks
- D5.3: Final report on methods for generating hazard event sets and quantifying risk
- D6.5 Online repository of storylines on multi-risk decision-making

Updated guiding questions for step 3: Characterization of indirect risk

The goal of step 3 is to characterize indirect risk arising because the direct effects of a hazard event can cause indirect effects. There are effects which are not directly caused by the hazard itself, but which are still linked to the event. Such damages can often materialize in a different geographical

area (i.e., in areas where the hazard did not actually hit) and at a later point in time (i.e., days, weeks, months after the event has taken place).

Indirect risks occur because sectors, systems, and communities are highly interdependent. A disruption in one part of the system can trigger a chain reaction that affects other parts—in different sectors or, as mentioned above, at a later time, and even in areas not directly impacted by the hazard. These effects are often amplified by the complexity of modern economies, infrastructure networks, ecological systems, and social structures. Examples of interdependencies include:

- Infrastructure interdependencies: A power outage (direct effect) can disrupt telecommunications, healthcare, and water supply systems (indirect effects).
- Economic interdependencies: Flooding in one region may disrupt supply chains regionally or even globally, impacting production and income in distant locations. Businesses not physically affected may still suffer losses due to reduced access to markets, raw materials, or labor.
- Social interdependencies: Damage to housing or displacement can lead to a breakdown in community networks, increased mental health burdens, and loss of educational continuity.
- Environmental interdependencies: Destruction of one ecosystem (e.g., wetlands) may reduce resilience in adjacent systems (e.g., increased flood risk downstream or biodiversity loss elsewhere).
- Institutional and policy interdependencies: Inadequate response in one jurisdiction may exacerbate impacts in neighboring areas due to shared governance or resource dependency.

In step 3, we characterize which of the system elements defined in step 1 and based on direct risk in step 2 would be indirectly affected. The aim is to understand how the system elements identified in steps 1 and 2—whether tangible (e.g., infrastructure, firms) or intangible (e.g., cultural heritage, biodiversity)—are indirectly affected through interconnections and dependencies. These pathways are shaped by *functional*, *spatial*, and *temporal* interdependencies. Importantly, indirect risks may manifest gradually, over weeks, months, or even years, and may be difficult to quantify if only traditional damage assessments are used. Also, these effects may be measured with market-based methods (e.g., economic output) or non-market indicators (e.g., social cohesion, mental health, biodiversity indices). Thus, both quantitative and qualitative methods may be applied to analyze indirect risks.

Example questions to consider in step 3 (questions are not in the order of asking nor prescribed, just for your consideration):

Indirect impacts

- What are the indirect impacts natural hazards have on your system elements which arise from a direct impact?
 - Such effects include, for instance, ripple effects along supply chains causing business or supply chain interruption, change in economic productivity.
- Which geographic areas or populations are affected indirectly—even if the hazard did not strike them directly?
- Please note that some of the impacts the system owner is experiencing do not come from the impact on their own system, but due to their connectedness and dependencies on other systems. So, can you identify dependencies between e.g. sectors, individual actors, ... that amplify or mediate indirect impacts?

- For instance, small-scale businesses in country X can be impacted due to a hazard impacting production in country Y, or one region's agriculture sector is dependent on energy or water infrastructure.
- Are there previous case studies or cross-sector analyses that illustrate indirect impact chains relevant to your system?
- In some cases, you might not have experience with previous events (e.g., due to a lack of historical events). In these cases, define indirect impacts based on plausible future events (e.g., by using the storylines approach, see <https://dashboard.myriadproject.eu/storylines-repository/>).

Dynamic Feedbacks and Cascading Effects

- Are there any feedback loops (positive or negative) where indirect impacts influence other elements of the system over time?
 - For example, an economic shock in one sector leading to unemployment, which in turn weakens household resilience in the face of future events.
- Can you map the timing of how indirect impacts unfold (e.g., using a timeline, impact chain, matrix or systems diagram)?
- How might a cascading failure occur—where the failure of one system element triggers failures in others?

Indirect risk metrics

- What are the main indirect impacts of interest for you as a system owner (e.g., sectors, institutions, local government)?
 - E.g., the transport sector might be interested in minimizing economic costs to transportation due to drought impacting agriculture. What are the metrics for these impacts? For example: Decreased economic output due to interruptions in supply chains.
 - Other examples include:
 - Economic: lost income, increased costs, GDP impact.
 - Environmental: biodiversity loss, degradation of ecosystem services.
 - Social: displacement, mental health issues, loss of social capital.
- In the case of working in a setting where historical events are few and limited, ask about which metric of indirect risk would be of interest for a plausible future event.

Dynamics of exposure, vulnerability, and impacts

- How do indirect impacts alter the exposure or vulnerability of your system (or others) to future hazards?
 - For example, an indirect economic loss may reduce a household's or business's capacity to prepare for future events.
- Are there populations, sectors or actors whose vulnerability increases due to indirect effects?
 - For instance, small businesses impacted by supply chain interruptions could have higher vulnerability in a case they are impacted by a hazard directly.

With these new insights gained, make sure to revisit steps 1 and 2 and make adjustments as needed.

Why might that be necessary?

During the assessment of indirect risk—such as supply chain disruptions from damaged transport routes—you might uncover critical interdependencies (e.g. reliance on external food distribution) that you did not initially consider. Therefore, you might have to return to **Step 1** to expand the system map, and/or to **Step 2** to better quantify the direct damage that triggers these cascading effects.

Step 3

Fictional example

Implementation of step 3:

- Damage to transport infrastructure influencing agricultural supply chains
- Agricultural losses influencing national and regional supply chains
- Increase in food insecurity
- Damage to transport infrastructure impacting accessibility to health care
- Large insurance payments increase premiums
- Increase in interest rates for loans
- Decrease in business performances across regions due to opportunity costs
- Decrease in productivity
 - Risk metrics: Costs of disrupted supply chains, decrease in purchasing power, increased indebtedness, ...

Examples from MYRIAD-EU

Scandinavia Pilot:

Implementation of step 3:

- Applied the GRACE macroeconomic model to simulate cascading cross-sectoral impacts.
- Incorporated 2018's drought, heat, and wildfire events to model indirect effects.
- Modeled labor shifts, price increases, and trade changes across multiple sectors and regions.

Canary Islands Pilot:

Implementation of step 3:

- Used Causal Loop Chains and multi-hazard scenarios (e.g. tropical storms, volcanic eruption).
- Developed a double-entry impact matrix to link hazards to cross-sector disruptions.
- Applied both qualitative and quantitative data (e.g. from GRAFCAN) for scenario modeling.

Table 5 Table listing the tools and/or methods applied per pilot for their implementation of step 3. For further examples of methods, tools and datasets or practices that could be helpful in the implementation of this step, we refer to the Disaster Risk Gateway.

Pilot	Tool/method used
Canary Islands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - Resilient Tourism Scorecard - Dynamic Vulnerability Model
Danube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ABM - DAPP - Statistical analysis of Figaro data - Storylines
North Sea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - Causal Chains
Scandinavia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GRACE - Storylines
Veneto	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - Stakeholder interviews

To date, the MYRIAD-EU team produced the following deliverables which can contribute to the operationalization of this step of the framework:

- D1.1 Wiki-style online crowdsourcing platform of multi-hazard, multi-risk methods, models, and tools (Disaster Risk Gateway)
- D4.2 Guidance on methodology for extracting empirical evidence from pilots
- D4.3 Report on novel methods for detecting empirical evidence of dynamics and feedback of risk drivers
- D4.4 Report on methods for quantifying the dynamics and feedbacks of multi-hazard risks
- D4.4 Methods for Quantifying the Dynamics and Feedbacks of Multi-Hazard Risk
- D5.2 Interim report on methods for generating hazard event sets and quantifying risks
- D5.3: Final report on methods for generating hazard event sets and quantifying risk
- D6.5 Online repository of storylines on multi-risk decision-making

Updated guiding questions for step 4: Evaluation of direct and indirect risk

The goal of step 4 is to evaluate the direct and indirect risk characterized in step 2 and step 3 and assess them according to a range of evaluation criteria. This evaluation helps prioritize which risks require management actions in step 5.

Example questions to consider in step 4 (*Note: questions are not in the order of asking nor prescribed, just for the reader's consideration*):

Risk evaluation criteria

Taking into account the various risk metrics evaluated in steps 2 and 3, determine which risks require action and should be managed or minimized. This assessment should be based on a comparison of the outcomes from both direct and indirect risk characterization against the established risk evaluation criteria. Some of these evaluation criteria are highlighted in the questions below.

- What criteria can you use to evaluate the effectiveness of your risk management measures? See the following examples of risk evaluation criteria and relevant risk metrics:
 - Frequency of occurrence: e.g., how often floods exceeding a certain threshold have occurred in the past 30 years.
 - Magnitude of consequences: e.g., estimated economic loss in euros per event or per year; number of people affected.
 - Exposure and vulnerability of assets: e.g., length of road infrastructure repeatedly damaged by landslides per year.
 - Recovery time: e.g., how long a critical service (e.g., transport, water) remains disrupted after an event.
 - Cost of risk reduction: e.g., cost of dyke repair compared to the avoided loss over 10 years.
 - Return period of triggering events: e.g., expected loss during a 1-in-100-year drought event.
 - Level of insurance coverage: e.g., proportion of damages that are financially covered vs. uninsured losses.
 - Social vulnerability indicators: e.g., number of low-income households affected.
 - Systemic interdependencies: e.g., risk cascading from damaged transport to supply chain interruptions.
- How can these metrics be evaluated? You can use the following approaches, amongst others, to evaluate and compare risk metrics (this is by no means a comprehensive list):
 - Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA): Useful when decisions must balance several quantitative and qualitative criteria (e.g., combining cost, social impact, and environmental consequences).
 - Cost-benefit analysis (CBA): Compare the cost of a risk reduction measure with the expected avoided damage over time.
 - Scenario-based stress testing: Evaluate how systems perform under different risk scenarios, including compound events.
 - Risk matrices or heatmaps: Visual tools to compare risks based on likelihood and consequence.
 - Geospatial analysis: Use maps and GIS data to visualize spatial distribution of risk and exposure.
 - Stakeholder scoring: Invite local experts and stakeholders to assign importance or urgency ratings to different risks based on their knowledge and priorities.
- What criteria can you use to decide which risks should be prioritized? You can use the following criteria, amongst others, to make a risk selection (this is by no means a comprehensive list):
 - Expected reduction in losses (economic, environmental, social)
 - Acceptability of residual risk after intervention
 - Feasibility under current governance and budget constraints
 - Alignment with policy/legal obligations
 - Co-benefits, e.g., ecological restoration from wetland flood protection
- What are the policy/legislative requirements to manage these direct and indirect risks?

- For instance, if a disaster risk management agency has legal responsibility for managing flood protection infrastructure in a certain area, they might focus on upgrading the protection. Similarly, insurance agencies will focus on risks that are covered by their policies.
- How do different evaluation criteria reflect if risks are manageable and if risk management options are feasible?
 - Are the risks under consideration actionable with current resources, technical capacities, and institutional mandates?
 - Do they fall within existing legal frameworks or require structural/policy change?
 - Are there risks whose complexity, uncertainty, or systemic nature makes them less manageable?
- How do current governance frameworks enhance or limit the ability to address and reduce risks?
- What is the cost-benefit ratio for risk reduction and management?
 - Stakeholders operate under finite and limited resources, and their decision-making might be led by costs versus benefits. Please note that cost-benefit ratio is just one of the options. The evaluation of risk can also consider co-benefits or less quantifiable outcomes, such as health and biodiversity.

Governance

- How are risk management responsibilities distributed among stakeholders? Who has the mandate and capacity to implement measures?
- What participatory processes are in place to involve local experts and stakeholders in defining risk thresholds?
- How do current governance frameworks enhance or limit the ability to address and reduce risks?

Communication of risk analysis with stakeholders

- What are the different ways to communicate the results of risk analysis as a part of risk evaluation?
 - For instance: risk maps, impact curves, risk indices, or consequence-likelihood matrices?
- To whom should the results of risk analysis be communicated and in what format?
 - Consider tailoring formats based on stakeholder type, e.g., visual summaries for local communities, technical dashboards for decision-makers.
- How should communication strategies be adapted for different stakeholders?
 - Different stakeholder groups (e.g., policymakers, emergency responders, local residents) require different levels of detail, formats, and delivery channels.
 - Use appropriate platforms: social media, community meetings, policy briefs, technical reports, or interactive tools.
- How can you incorporate stakeholder feedback to prevent conflicts (e.g. between sectors)?

Selection of risks to focus on

- Based on the evaluation criteria, what are the risks you will be considering risk management options for in step 5? Prioritize risks that are not only critical but also feasible to address. See the following examples for prioritization:
 - Focus on reducing drought risks in a high-value agricultural region based on recurring loss patterns and critical water availability thresholds.

- Invest in dyke repairs in a flood-prone urban area with high insured assets and large population exposure.
- Target road sections with high damage frequency and long repair times, which critically disrupt logistics and access.
- **Note that it might not be possible to manage all risks, so focus on those which are feasible in a given context, more urgent, and have highest levels of interdependencies**

With these new insights gained, make sure to revisit previous framework steps and make adjustments as needed.

Why might that be necessary?

In evaluating which risks require management, you may find that some high-impact but slow-onset risks (e.g. mental health effects from displacement due to a flooding) were not adequately represented in the earlier characterisation. This might have you revisit **Step 3** to improve indirect risk metrics, or even to **Step 1** to reassess system vulnerabilities.

Step 4

Fictional example

Implementation of step 4:

- Availability of water for agricultural irrigation
- Dyke repair cost impact on risk owner annual income
- Amount of losses insured
- Event of a specific return period and associated loss
- How long and how often a specific road infrastructure is damaged

Examples from MYRIAD-EU

North Sea Pilot:

Implementation of step 4:

- Stakeholder-driven prioritization of hazards across sectors (e.g. droughts, cold spells).
- Evaluated relevance and frequency of hazards in terms of actual threat.
- Considered sector-specific vulnerabilities, e.g., negligible impact of rare earthquakes.

Canary Islands:

Implementation of step 4:

- Created a Destination Resilience Scorecard (DRS) for tourism governance.
- Used participatory validation to define acceptable risk thresholds.
- Leveraged forensic disaster analysis (e.g., La Palma volcanic eruption).

Table 6 Table listing the tools and/or methods applied per pilot for their implementation of step 4. For further examples of methods, tools and datasets or practices that could be helpful in the implementation of this step, we refer to the Disaster Risk Gateway.

Pilot	Tool/method used
Canary Islands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - Destination Resilience Scorecard (DRS)
Danube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CATSIM - DAPP-MR
North Sea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - Stakeholder interviews - Framework and guidance protocols - Causal loop diagrams
Scandinavia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - GRACE model
Veneto	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - Stakeholder interviews - Focus Group discussions - COAST-Aid (COastal multi-risk Assessment SupportEd by AI-based tools)

To date, the MYRIAD-EU team produced the following deliverables which can contribute to the operationalization of this step of the framework:

- D5.2 Interim report on methods for generating hazard event sets and quantifying risks
- D5.3: Final report on methods for generating hazard event sets and quantifying risk

Updated guiding questions for step 5: Identifying risk management options

The goal of step 5 is to come up with risk management options for direct and indirect risks selected to be managed in step 4. This step is broken down into three sub-steps to guide users through a manageable and logical sequence of actions:

5.1: Identify a broad range of risk management options

Start by generating a comprehensive list of possible risk management options that address the prioritized risks from step 4. Include measures that span the entire Disaster Risk Management (DRM) cycle: prevention, preparedness, response, and recovery. Consider both structural and non-structural options, and recognize different approaches to risk (quantitative, precautionary, participatory).

Here are some guiding questions to consider:

- What risk management options are available/needed to address the risks you selected in step 4
- Have you considered options across all DRM phases (prevention, preparedness, response, recovery)?
- What structural measures (e.g., flood barriers, infrastructure reinforcement) and non-structural measures (e.g., land-use policies, early warning systems, public awareness campaigns) are relevant?
- Are your options:
 - Risk-informed (e.g., based on thresholds, modeled impacts)?
 - Precautionary (e.g., containment strategies, monitoring)?
 - Expert elicitation or participatory-based (e.g., developed through expert consultation or citizen engagement)?
- What are the key uncertainties involved in each option?

5.2: Assess feasibility and prioritize options

Evaluate each option based on a set of practical and contextual criteria to determine which ones are urgent, feasible, effective, and appropriate. Consider financial, technical, institutional, and social factors. This helps filter and prioritize options for implementation.

Here are some guiding questions to consider:

- Which risks need to be addressed most urgently and can they be addressed feasibly?
- Which options are feasible given financial, technical, institutional, and political constraints?
- What level of risk reduction is achieved by each option? Are there residual risks?
- What is the social acceptability of the proposed options among stakeholders?
- How do risk management options address vulnerable populations or promote social equity? Are there measures in place to ensure that vulnerable populations' needs are considered in the process?
- Are there any multi-hazard synergies (e.g., one measure addresses multiple risks)?
- In case you are considering a multi-hazard situation, what are synergies (i.e., option for managing the risk of one hazard decreases the risk of another hazard) and asynergies (i.e., option for managing a risk of one hazard increases the risk of another hazard) between different risk management options? In the case of asynergies, are there any plans in place to manage these?

5.3: Plan implementation of selected risk management options

For the prioritized options, define a clear and realistic implementation plan. This includes sequencing, assigning responsibilities, setting timelines, and estimating resources needed. Also, consider how implementation outcomes will be monitored and adjusted over time.

Here are some guiding questions to consider:

- What is the timeline for implementing each option (short-, medium-, or long-term)?
- What is the sequencing of actions? Are some preconditions required before others can be implemented?
- Who is responsible for implementing each measure? Are institutional roles clear?
- What are the estimated costs and funding sources?
- How can feedback from stakeholders be integrated during and after implementation?
- Are there institutional or governance changes needed to enable implementation?

- At what system level do your options operate (local, sectoral, regional)? Do the benefits or risks cascade across sectors or areas?

With these new insights gained, make sure to revisit previous framework steps and make adjustments as needed.

Why might that be necessary?

When thinking about potential management options—such as upgrading early-warning systems—you may realize that previously neglected actors (e.g., local health providers) are critical for the implementation of these management options or that players of an economic sector, that you were previously unaware of, are affected by certain management measures. This could require you to revisit **Step 1** to adjust the governance mapping or **Step 4** to re-evaluate the relevance of certain risks based on institutional capacity.

Step 5

Fictional example

Implementation of step 5:

- Reservoirs and land use management for drought and flood risk reduction
- Subsurface flood water harvesting systems
- Integrated early warning systems
- Development of integrated policy risk management frameworks
- Developing joint funds for multi-hazard and multi-risk management
- Public-private partnerships

Examples from MYRIAD-EU

Canary Islands Pilot:

Implementation of step 5:

- Developed sector-specific measures (e.g. tourism, agrifood) based on literature and interviews.
- Created a scorecard to assess measures by different criteria.
- Built a Cross-sectoral Risk Management Matrix (e.g. positive/negative/unknown sectoral impacts).

North Sea Pilot:

Implementation of step 5:

- Identified and validated risk management measures with stakeholders.
- Built a Cross-sectoral Risk Management Matrix (e.g. impact of opening wind farms to shipping).
- Categorized effects (positive, negative, neutral, unknown) across sectors.

Table 7 Table listing the tools and/or methods applied per pilot for their implementation of step 5. For further examples of methods, tools and datasets or practices that could be helpful in the implementation of this step, we refer to the Disaster Risk Gateway.

Pilot	Tool/method used
Canary Islands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - Desk review - Stakeholder discussions - Tourism Resilience Scorecard - Cross-sectoral Risk Management Matrix
Danube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DAPP-MR - CATSIM - Storylines - Stakeholder discussions - Risk layering - Desk review
North Sea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - Stakeholder interviews - Stakeholder workshops - Cross-sectoral Risk Management Matrix
Scandinavia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DAPP-MR - Storylines
Veneto	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - UCPM Peer Review Assessment Framework - Stakeholder interviews - Focus group discussions

To date, the MYRIAD-EU team produced the following deliverables which can contribute to the operationalization of this step of the framework:

- D1.1 Wiki-style online crowdsourcing platform of multi-hazard, multi-risk methods, models, and tools (Disaster Risk Gateway)
- D4.2 Guidance on methodology for extracting empirical evidence from pilots

Updated guiding questions for step 6: Accounting for future system state

The goal of step 6 is to consider how the system may evolve over time in light of larger dynamic processes (e.g., climate and environmental change, demographic trends, economic shifts) and the impact of the risk management options selected in step 5. This step is not only about external changes but also about how the system adapts and transforms as a result of the very measures introduced to manage risks.

Given the current evaluation and strategies against the effects of multi-hazards, the objective here is to critically evaluate whether these strategies will remain effective in various plausible future settings—or whether they might fail—and how to adaptively navigate risk under such uncertain conditions. This includes understanding different sectoral priorities and planning horizons, and how to incorporate uncertainty and system dynamics into forward-looking risk governance.

The DAPP-MR approach, developed by WP6, aligns closely with the goal of Step 6 of the framework as it requires its users to plan flexible strategies that can adapt over time as conditions change. It looks at different possible futures and identifies points where current strategies might no longer work (so-called Adaptation Tipping Points). By mapping out adaptive pathways under unstable scenarios—including dynamic changes in hazards, exposure, and vulnerability—DAPP-MR shows when and how to adjust plans depending on how risks develop. This method supports decision-making under uncertainty and thus complements Step 6 of the framework well.

Example questions to consider in step 6 (questions are not in the order of asking nor prescribed, just for the reader's consideration):

Influence of larger processes

- What are the various broader influences that could potentially impact your system? These influences may include factors such as climate change, urbanization, economic shifts, demographic trends, etc. Consider how all of these influences could potentially alter elements within the system, such as its boundaries, exposure, vulnerability, and hazard characteristics, including frequency and magnitude.
- What is the relevant timeframe for each key influence? Consider sector-specific timelines: e.g., forestry may operate with 30–50-year outlooks, while energy or agriculture may focus on 1–10-year timescales. How do these differing planning horizons influence your integrated risk management strategy? Note that a long-term perspective is of crucial importance (e.g., for climate change).
- What are the uncertainties involved in these processes? How do you account for uncertainties in hazard occurrence, exposure, system feedbacks, and long-term socio-environmental changes?
- What are the plausible future system states that risk management must be robust or adaptive to? How are these scenarios constructed, and what assumptions underlie them?

Influence of considered risk management options

- How do the risk management measures introduced in step 5 influence the system's long-term evolution? For example, do they reduce vulnerability in the short term but increase exposure in the long run (e.g., through induced development or system dependency)? How will these perform under future system change taking into account wider influences (examples above).
- Could these options introduce new risks or increase risks in other areas or sectors (i.e., risk transfer or maladaptation)?
- How do these options perform under different plausible futures? Do they remain effective, or are there points at which they fail?

Governance

- How can your governance framework encourage cross-sector collaboration or innovative partnerships to address complex risks?
- How can your governance structures enable cross-sectoral dialogue and collaboration, considering the differing timeframes and priorities among sectors?

Flexibility and Innovation

- How flexible and adaptive are your current risk management frameworks in the face of unexpected changes?
- Does your governance framework allow for iterative adjustments, learning, and innovation?
- Are there mechanisms to review and revise strategies over time as more is learned about system responses and emerging risks?

With a definition of the future system state outlined, walk through the framework's steps 1-5 again and refine your analysis as needed.

Why might that be necessary?

Considering future changes like urban expansion or a shift in climate-induced hazard may reveal to you that today's risk management options will not be viable long-term. This might require you to return to **Step 5** to redesign management options, or even to **Step 1** to redefine system boundaries and exposure patterns under future scenarios.

Step 6

Fictional example

Implementation of step 6:

- Risk management options:
- Reservoirs and land use management for drought and flood risk reduction
- Subsurface flood water harvesting systems
- Integrated early warning systems
- Development of integrated policy risk management frameworks
- Developing joint funds for multi-hazard and multi-risk management
- Public-private partnerships

Examples from MYRIAD-EU

Veneto Pilot

Implementation of step 6:

- Used quantitative ML models (e.g., DBSCAN, MLP) to simulate future hazard footprints to 2100.U
- Included climate scenarios RCP 2.6, 4.5, 8.5 and land use change for ecosystems/agriculture.
- Incorporated PRAF (Peer Review Assessment Framework) for DRM pathways.

Canary Islands Pilot:

Implementation of step 6:

- Used La Palma volcanic eruption to build "Back to Normal" vs. "Better Built" recovery pathways.
- Assessed DRR-recovery feedback loops under tourism redevelopment scenarios.
- Focused on how recovery choices today shape exposure and vulnerability tomorrow.

Table 8 Table listing the tools and/or methods applied per pilot for their implementation of step 6. For further examples of methods, tools and datasets or practices that could be helpful in the implementation of this step, we refer to the Disaster Risk Gateway.

Pilot	Tool/method used
Canary Islands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DAPP-MR - Storylines - Desk review - Multi-Hazard Risk Scenario Tool
Danube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DAPP-MR - Storylines - Stakeholder discussions - Desk review - CATSIM
North Sea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DAPP-MR - Storylines - Stakeholder workshops
Scandinavia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DAPP-MR - Storylines - Stakeholder interviews
Veneto	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storylines - Supervised ML methods - Multi-hazard footprints - Multi-Layer Perceptron algorithm - Risk assessment for ecosystems, water quality, agriculture

To date, the MYRIAD-EU team in WP6 suggested two possible approaches to thinking about future system state: 1) the Storyline Approach, and 2) DAPP-MR (Schlumberger et al., 2022).

- D3.3b Interim report on implementation and testing of MYRIAD-EU methods and tools in each Pilot
- D6.4 Final report on collaborative systems and DAPP approaches to develop forward-looking DRM pathways
- D6.5 Online repository of storylines on multi-risk decision-making

Some guidance on stakeholder engagement

Stakeholder engagement is crucial across different steps of the framework. Navigating and facilitating a stakeholder engagement process is a delicate task because of the variety of stakeholders who are affected by hazards and involved in the risk management process. There are a variety of approaches to facilitating stakeholder selection, engagement, and management (e.g., various stakeholder identification techniques, participatory online, in-person, and hybrid workshops) that have been covered extensively in WP3's work and should be fully considered and tailored to the context.

Some considerations for stakeholder engagement:

- Who are the main stakeholders you need to consider when assessing risk and selecting risk management options? Think broadly across sectors and governance levels.
- What are the interests, incentives, and mandates of these stakeholders? What potential conflicts or power imbalances exist? How will these be managed?
- Are these stakeholders actively involved in decision-making? If so, at what stage and to what extent? Are they involved in co-defining risk priorities and management options?

To support this, we suggest using a *multi-level, co-development approach to stakeholder engagement*.

At key steps of the framework, hold co-development workshops, i.e. structured, facilitated workshops or panels that bring together stakeholders across governance levels (local, regional, national) and sectors. These workshops help bridge technical analysis with stakeholder knowledge by providing a neutral, inclusive space to:

- Share and integrate local knowledge (e.g., on historical hazard impacts, vulnerabilities, and local capacity),
- Align with regional and national policy objectives and constraints,
- Jointly define system boundaries (step 1), relevant risk metrics (steps 2–3), and appropriate evaluation criteria (step 4),
- Select and sequence risk management options that are feasible, acceptable, and fair (step 5),
- Reflect on future system trajectories and long-term needs (step 6).

This approach helps ensure stakeholder voices are heard not only during validation, but throughout the analytical and decision-making processes.

Some practical engagement methods to consider for the individual framework steps include:

- step 1 (System definition): Use participatory mapping or storytelling techniques to identify key hazards, affected elements, and exposure areas. Include governance mapping exercises to understand roles and responsibilities across levels.
- steps 2–3 (Direct and indirect risk characterisation): Co-select risk metrics via ranking or Delphi methods; allow space for both quantitative metrics (e.g., insured loss) and qualitative ones (e.g., cultural value, mental health impacts).
- step 4 (Risk evaluation): Co-develop evaluation criteria based on local urgency, political mandates, feasibility, or equity considerations.
- step 5 (Option selection): Facilitate option-scoring exercises, scenario testing, and impact pathway mapping across sectors.
- step 6 (Future system state): Involve stakeholders in exploring how system elements might evolve due to climate, economic, or governance changes and how this may affect risk management outcomes.

Tipp!

Building climate and disaster risk literacy among stakeholders—whether local, regional, or national—is essential for the effective and efficient application of the framework. The better stakeholders understand key risk concepts, the more meaningfully they can engage in co-defining challenges, selecting risk metrics, and evaluating management options. Therefore, investing in capacity-building and increasing risk understanding is a critical enabler of the entire process.

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